

Mood

Anxiety and low mood

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Mood

Lack of motivation

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Mood

Feeling
isolated

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Mood

Fear of trying new things

Existing tools

Using these tools in this scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help and support videos?

Help?

Mood

**Difficulty
with self
belief and
imposter
syndrome**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Mood

**Difficulty
managing
emotions**

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

Mood

Difficulty
with handling
the unknown
or
unexpected

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

Help?

Mood

Need of
support in
getting things
done

Existing tools

Using these tools in this
scenario makes me feel...

What would help?

A platform for help
and support videos?

Help?

